

MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGICAL ROLE OF INFORMATION EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

Kucharov Sardorbek Akmalovich

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the technological education department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10636550>

Abstract. *This article provides information on the modern innovative technological role of informational education in the process of technological education, and innovative methods of preparing students for practical activities, work, and continuing education.*

Keywords: *innovation, traditional, non-traditional, collaborative learning, modeling, research, project.*

The word innovation appeared in the Latin language in the middle of the 17th century and means the introduction of a new field into a certain field and the emergence of a number of changes in this field. This means that innovation, on the one hand, is not the process of implementing innovation, but the activity of transforming innovation into a specific social practice. Innovative activity in its full development includes interrelated types of work, the totality of which ensures the emergence of real innovations. Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now in traditional education students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

Today, educational technologies can be conditionally divided into two types:

1. Traditional
2. Unconventional

Traditional educational technology - intended for a certain period, the educational process is more focused on the teacher, using the traditional form of teaching, methods and a set of educational tools. is to achieve the goal of education.

Non-traditional educational technology - designed for a specific period, with the student at the center of the educational process, a modern form of teaching, active teaching methods and a set of modern didactic tools is intended for educational work. is to guide the achievement of a goal and a guaranteed result.

Non-traditional educational technology differs from traditional educational technology in that it creates conditions for the development of students' cognitive abilities, special attention is paid to their independent work, and cognitive activities are exploratory and creative in nature. The structure of the lesson will be variable.

In turn, non-traditional educational technology is divided into three:

- Collaborative learning

- Modeling
- Research (Project)

Collaborative learning is teaching and learning based on the organization of sequential use of skills and qualifications under the direct leadership of the student, which ensures the reproductive activity of students in assimilation, assimilation, and strengthening of knowledge.

It consists of methods that allow students to learn by working in independent groups. These include methods such as working with a book, educational discussion, round discussion, brainstorming, working in small groups, and debate.

Modeling is the creation of a condensed and simplified view of events and processes that occur in real life and society in the audience, and provides for the personal participation of students in them and learning through activities. Its main goal is to increase the efficiency of the educational process by ensuring that students are not only listening, but also directly involved in acquiring knowledge. These can include methods such as these games and role-playing games.

Research is a set of methods that enhance and encourage students' understanding and solving of problems, independent learning. The purpose of the research is to arouse students' interest in asking questions and searching for answers during the lesson. Teaching in it ensures direct participation of students in the process of practical research. These include methods such as problem situation, design method, independent research, and reference text.

Pedagogical tasks of the science "Technology" are determined by its unique contribution to solving the main tasks of the general education of a person.

1. Forming students' knowledge about technology and developing their thinking.
2. Forming a technical outlook. In solving this important task, the entire pedagogical team participates in the process of teaching all subjects.
3. Education in the spirit of national ideology.

Preparing students for practical activities, work, and continuing education. None of the above issues should be solved in isolation. They should be implemented as a whole and closely related to each other. It is possible to train students' thinking and create a technical worldview only on the basis of solid mastery of technology science. On the other hand, only by teaching logical thinking, it is possible to achieve a deep understanding of the specific aspects of technology as a science. In addition, in order to achieve the correct solution of the task of preparing technology for practical activities in the process of teaching technology, it is necessary to increase the scientific technology. Only if they can make correct and deep conclusions, students can take a critical and creative approach to solving each problem, do not lose themselves in front of new problems, and can work effectively in different conditions. Also, practical work expands students' worldview and enriches it with new facts, and increases the level of knowledge of technology, ensuring that it is deep, complete and solid.

In the educational process of general secondary education DTS, new pedagogical technology, educational programs, development of organizational and management functions in general democratic principles, consideration of students as individuals, democratization of the educational process, socialization, school as a social institution determines the main directions of general education schools, considering the introduction of rights expansion.

Covering pre-school, general secondary, special secondary, vocational and post-secondary stages and suitable for non-specialists in technology and practical training. The intended science of "Technology" is based on a new system of regulations and views for technology:

- the entire "life cycle" of the frame should be taken into account;
- teaching of technology-related subjects should reflect changes in the content of education, taking into account the current state of the world and development prospects;
- it is necessary to abandon the need to teach non-technologists in theoretical classes;
- should be built on the basis of the didactic principles of technology education;
- the renewal and relevance of the content of technical production training courses can be extended only on the basis of emphasizing the principles of information processing;
- focus on guaranteeing the qualities of training, upbringing and development of a person;
- redistribution of study time resources in favor of development of students' thinking, organization of creative educational activities.

The important elements of the innovative pedagogical process are self-management and self-mobilization of the individual. One of its most important directions is the development of students' cognitive activity, which leads to the activation of students' academic work and professional specialization.

An axiological approach to innovative activity means that a person devotes himself to the process of creating new things, pedagogical values created by him.

It is up to the teacher and the student to choose the technology to achieve the result according to the goal, because the main goal of both parties is clear: to achieve the result it is necessary to work with a computer, perhaps a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology will be needed, it depends on the teacher and the student.

REFERENCES

1. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). SECTION: TECHNICAL SCIENCE. TRANSPORT. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS, 128.
2. Akmalovich, K. S. (2023). TEXNOLOGIK TA'LIM YO'NALISHIDA SMART O'QITISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI, 59.
3. Кучаров, С. (2023). Texnologik ta'lim yo 'nalishida mutaxassislik fanlarini o 'qitishining asosiy shakllari. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/5), 171-181.
4. Choriev, R., & Kucharov, S. (2023). THE ROLE OF PRODUCTION EDUCATION IN THE VOCATIONAL TRAINING PROCESS. *Science and innovation*, 2(A8), 93-96.
5. Kucharovich, O. A., Akmalovich, K. S., & Qorajonovich, Z. A. (2023). Methodology of Teaching Technology in Secondary Schools.
6. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). SECTION: TECHNICAL SCIENCE. TRANSPORT. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS, 128.
7. SA Kucharov (2023). TEXNOLOGIK TA'LIM YO'NALISHIDA SMART O'QITISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI-Analysis of world scientific views *International Scientific ...*, 2023.
8. ХЧ Дусяров, СА Кўчаров - ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМДА УЗВИЙЛИК ФАНИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ВА АМАЛИЙ АСОСЛАРИ - Zamonaviy fan va ta'lim yangiliklari xalqaro ilmiy jurnal, 2023.
9. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). SECTION: TECHNICAL SCIENCE. TRANSPORT. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS, 128.

10. SA Kucharov - Analysis of world scientific views International Scientific. **TEKNOLOGIK TA'LIM YO 'NALISHIDA SMART O 'QITISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI**, 2023.
11. Кучаров, С. (2023). **Technologik ta'lim yo 'nalishida mutaxassislik fanlarini o 'qitishining asosiy shakllari**. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/S), 171-181.
12. Odayev, A. K. C. (2023). **BALANCING DETAIL AND ASSEMBLY COMBINATIONS**. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(3), 189-195.
13. Choriev, R., & Kucharov, S. (2023). **THE ROLE OF PRODUCTION EDUCATION IN THE VOCATIONAL TRAINING PROCESS**. *Science and innovation*, 2(A8), 93-96.
14. Kucharovich, O. A., Akmalovich, K. S., & Qorajonovich, Z. A. (2023). **Methodology of Teaching Technology in Secondary Schools**.
15. Кучаров, С. А., & Шағдаров, Н. (2021). **ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШДА АХБОРОТ ВА ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ**. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (1-Махсус сон), 119-122.
16. Кучаров, С. А. (2021). **ТЕКНОЛОГИЯ ТА'LIMI O 'QITUVCHISINING TEKNOLOGIK MADANIYATI**. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (1-Махсус сон), 116-118.
17. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). **SECTION: TECHNICAL SCIENCE. TRANSPORT. MODERN SCIENTIFIC CHALLENGES AND TRENDS**, 128.
18. Kucharov, A. S., Bobojonov, A. B., Kamalova, E. A., Ishmanova, D. N., & Ishmukhamedov, B. J. (2022). **Digitalization of the Strategic Management Systems of the Oil and Gas Industry Enterprises**. In *Big Data in the GovTech System* (pp. 119-125). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
19. Choriev, R., & Kucharov, S. (2023). **OPPORTUNITIES OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS**. *Science and innovation*, 2(B4), 152-155.
20. Odayev, A., Qalandarov, R., & Xolmatov, B. (2023). **PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF REPAIRING BLOCKS AND CYLINDER LINERS**. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES*, 4(1), 97-99.
21. Ko'charov, S. (2022). **PREPARATION OF PROFESSIONAL TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES**. *Физико-технологического образование*, (3).
22. Choriev, R., & Kucharov, S. (2023). **METHODOLOGY OF USING ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS IN THE FIELD OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION**. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 371-373.
23. Dusyarov, X. C., Odayev, A. K., & Kucharov, S. A. (2021). **Criteria for assessing student knowledge in technology classes**. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 1168-1173.
24. Kucharov, A. S. (2022). **IMPLEMENTATION OF "SMART AGRICULTURE" TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE COMPLEX OF UZBEKISTAN**. *Архив научных исследований*, 2(1).

25. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). Innovative Teaching Methods and their Practical Application in Technological Education Classes. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(5), 305-309.
26. Choriev, R. K., Khujakeldiev, K. N., Kucharov, S. A., Khayitova, S. D., Abdiev, N., & Amirqulov, X. Q. (2022). Pedagogical Problems Of Distance And Traditional Education. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 2895-2904.